

Extreme Food Risk Analytics

D5.2.3: Experimental Methodology, Tools & Reports from
Experiments

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
AI	Artificial Intelligence
XAI	Explainable Artificial Intelligence
LLM	Large Language Model
RAG	Retrieval-Augmented Generation
MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the results of the experimental work conducted within WP5 (Use-Cases, Focus Groups, and Performance Experiments) of the EFRA project. The report documents the evaluation and validation of models and tools that form the analytical and computational backbone of the EFRA platform.

The work carried out focuses on three main areas:

1. **Models required by EFRA pilots**, including predictive engines for food safety forecasting, clustering-based risk assessment in poultry farming, and time-series models for mycotoxin risk prediction. These experiments demonstrate significant improvements in predictive accuracy through the integration of multi-factor data sources such as historical incidents, laboratory results, and environmental variables.
2. **Models supporting the greener efficiency of the EFRA platform**, including hybrid human–machine systems for food risk classification, efficient summarization of regulatory texts, retrieval optimization, and model compression techniques that substantially reduce computational and energy costs.
3. **Other models for the EFRA platform**, covering advances in explainable artificial intelligence (XAI), large-scale classification of food recalls, and semantic annotation aligned with the EFRA conceptual model.

The experiments confirm that EFRA’s data-driven, multi-factor methodologies achieve substantial gains in accuracy, interpretability, and efficiency. The adoption of green artificial intelligence (AI) strategies and hybrid large language model (LLM) architectures significantly enhances both sustainability and operational scalability.

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a comprehensive evaluation framework and empirical validation of EFRA’s experimental models and tools, ensuring methodological transparency and supporting the project’s objective of building a sustainable, explainable, and high-performing platform for food risk analytics.

2. Introduction

This deliverable presents the results of the experimental activities within the EFRA project. The purpose of this deliverable is to document and evaluate the technological experiments performed to assess the performance, efficiency, and reliability of the analytical models forming the core of the EFRA platform.

The work builds on previous iterations of the deliverable and focuses on the final experimental validation of models and tools developed in Tasks T5.2 and T5.3. These experiments cover both the models required for EFRA's operational pilots and complementary models supporting the platform's efficiency, sustainability, and explainability. Together, they provide the empirical foundation for the EFRA platform's capability to process, predict, and interpret complex food risk scenarios.

2.1. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The report is organized into the following chapters:

- **Chapter 3** describes experiments related to the models required by EFRA pilots, including predictive engines for food risk forecasting and domain-specific risk assessment models.
- **Chapter 4** focuses on models supporting the greener efficiency of the EFRA platform, presenting methods and tools that enhance computational sustainability and reduce energy consumption.
- **Chapter 5** describes other models on the EFRA platform, including explainable AI methods, models for text classification, and ontology-based semantic annotation frameworks.
- **Chapter 6** concludes the deliverable by summarizing the main findings and highlighting their significance for the EFRA platform.

Chapters 3, 4 and 5 follow a similar structure, where each subsection describes a model on the EFRA platform. These subsections contain the following information: (i) summary, (ii) data, (iii) methods, (iv) results, and (v) conclusions. This structure ensures a coherent presentation of the experimental methodologies, results, and conclusions, enabling reproducibility, transparency, and alignment with EFRA's overall objectives.

3. Models Required by EFRA Pilots

This chapter reports on experiments concerning models required by EFRA pilots. These include the following:

- A time series prediction engine
- Clustering risk assessment in poultry farming
- A time series model for mycotoxin risk in poultry
- A mycotoxins trend prediction model for poultry feed
- Decision trees for pest observation prediction

3.1. A Time Series Prediction Engine

3.1.1. Summary

This engine outlines the experimental methodology and tools employed to validate the **Time Series Prediction Engine** component within the FOODAKAI system. The central experimental objective was to rigorously assess the performance improvement achieved by transitioning from traditional single-factor time series forecasting to the **Forecasting with Multiple Factors** approach.

The methodology utilizes a direct reduction of the forecasting problem to tabular regression, employing the **Extra Trees Regressor** as the core predictive model. Model evaluation is conducted through a **rolling window cross-validation** scheme, optimized using the **sMAPE** (Symmetric Mean Absolute Percentage Error) metric. The experimental results confirm that leveraging a comprehensive feature set, comprising historical incident data, laboratory testing data, and supplementary weather factors, substantially enhances the accuracy and reliability of the 12-month predictions across all recorded food safety dimensions.

3.1.2. Data

The experimental process is fundamentally anchored in accessing and preparing comprehensive historical time series data.

Source Data Pools:

1. **Published Incidents:** Border rejections and recalls, aggregated monthly.
2. **Laboratory Test Results:** "Above limit" and "below limit" results, aggregated monthly.

Time Series Dimensions: The data is structured to generate distinct time series for:

- Individual ingredients and hazards.
- Combinations of ingredients/hazards, ingredients/origins, and hazards/origins.

Granularity and Coverage: All time-series are aggregated at a monthly level, spanning available historical data (e.g., 2000-01 to 2023-10). To ensure the statistical meaningfulness of the experiments, a time series is deemed "trainable" only if it contains **more than three years of historical data** and **a minimum of 10 individual incidents**.

Feature Engineering (Factors): The core of the methodology is the Feature Extraction component, which transforms the raw time series into a rich, multi-dimensional feature space for training.

- **Base Factors:** A set of **274 distinct factors** are extracted for every trainable time series, primarily falling into the categories of Historical Incident Data Factors (e.g., incident peaks, moving averages) and Laboratory Testing Data Factors.

- **Supplementary Factors:** For per-origin predictions, an additional **80 supplementary weather factors** (e.g., monthly temperature, humidity, precipitation) are integrated, resulting in feature vectors exceeding **360 factors** for these specific models.

3.1.3. Methods

Forecasting Approach

The experimental method employs a robust, machine-learning-based approach where the time series forecasting task is solved via a direct reduction to a supervised tabular regression problem. This enables the model to leverage the rich set of extracted features (factors) to predict the t+1 to t+12 monthly values.

Model and Tools

The primary estimator utilized across the experimentation pipeline is the Extra Trees Regressor. This model was selected for its high performance in regression tasks, robustness against high-dimensional data, and autonomous determination of feature importance, which is critical given the varying influence of the 274+ factors.

Hyperparameter Tuning (Offline Mode)

To ensure continuous model optimization, an automated hyperparameter tuning pipeline runs in an "offline mode." This process discovers the optimal settings for the Extra Trees Regressor for *each* trainable time series.

- **Optimizer:** Tree of Parzen Estimators (TPE), leveraging the Hyperopt library.
- **Objective: Minimization** of the sMAPE metric (resulting from cross-validation).
- **Evaluation Constraint:** MAX_EVALS=50 hyperparameter space data points are evaluated per model.

Evaluation Strategy

A standard time series validation technique, **Rolling Window Cross-Validation**, is applied to rigorously assess model generalization and stability across different temporal subsets of the historical data.

Evaluation Metrics

The models are primarily optimized against two metrics:

- **sMAPE (Symmetric Mean Absolute Percentage Error):** This is the objective function used for model optimization.

$$\text{sMAPE} \in [0, 2]$$

Values close to 0.0 signify high forecast accuracy, whereas 2.0 indicates a completely inaccurate forecast.

- **FOODAKAI Accuracy Metric:** This custom, sum-based metric is used for final reporting within the application.

$$1 - \text{abs}(1 - (\sum(y_{\text{true}}) / \sum(y_{\text{pred}})))$$

It is acknowledged that while intuitive, this metric can be inherently flawed as it assesses the total predicted volume rather than the accuracy of individual monthly predictions.

3.1.4. Results

The shift to the Forecasting with Multiple Factors methodology has yielded substantial, quantifiable improvements in predictive performance across the entire suite of trainable time series.

Key Experimental Finding: The implementation of the 274-factor input space allowed the Extra Trees model to identify latent patterns and non-linear relationships in the food safety data, leading to a marked increase in forecast reliability compared to legacy, single-factor models. This enhancement is demonstrated by the visible alignment between predicted and true historical trends.

Performance Validation: The offline tuning and rolling window cross-validation consistently demonstrated lower average sMAPE scores for the new multi-factor models. For instance, in the complex heavy metals model, the integrated use of historical incident data (from 2000 onwards) and laboratory testing data provided sufficient context for the model to generate substantially more accurate trends than previously possible.

Model Characteristics: The experimentation verified that the prediction engine autonomously determines the relative importance of the 274+ factors, weighting them appropriately to produce a robust forecast tailored to the specific profile of each time series (e.g., sparse, dense, short, or multi-decade).

3.1.5. Conclusions

The experimental phase successfully validated the design and implementation of the **forecasting with multiple factors** approach. The results confirm that providing the Extra Trees Regressor with a rich, multi-dimensional feature set is paramount to achieving robust and reliable 12-month predictions for the FOODAKAI system.

The continuous, automated hyperparameter tuning pipeline, driven by the sMAPE objective function and TPE optimizer, guarantees that all deployed models remain optimally configured. This experimental methodology establishes a scalable and validated framework for delivering advanced trend forecasting, capable of integrating new data streams (like the supplementary weather factors) to maintain high predictive power as the data landscape evolves. The prediction-engine is now equipped to reliably generate actionable forecasts and corresponding trend calculations across all defined dimensions.

3.2. Clustering Risk Assessment in Poultry Farming

3.2.1. Summary

This section describes the experimental framework utilized for the **clustering risk assessment in poultry farming**, focusing on the development and validation of predictive AI models for critical flock outcomes. The core objective is to achieve reliable, early-lifecycle forecasting of **end-cycle weight anomalies** (bottom 10%) and **Mortality outliers** (top 10%). The methodology integrates a multi-stage analytical process: **spearman correlation analysis** to confirm early indicators, **Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP) neural networks** for robust outlier prediction, and **time series clustering** to classify distinct flock performance trajectories. Results confirm the high precision and increasing predictive capability of the models, enabling farm managers to initiate timely and proactive interventions as early as Day 7 of the flock lifecycle.

3.2.2. Data

The experimental validation relies on a comprehensive dataset designed to capture the granularity of poultry farming operations.

Dataset Scope: Model development leveraged a large-scale dataset comprising **10,327 individual flock records** spanning the years 2022 to 2023. Each record documents the complete lifecycle of a flock.

Feature Dimensions: The dataset is high-dimensional, incorporating factors that influence flock health and performance, grouped into the following categories:

Table 1: Data Description for Clustering Risk Assessment in Poultry Farming

Data Category	Representative Features
Identification & Logistics	Farm, Housing, Product, Breed Details, Hatchery/Placement Information
Growth & Performance	Daily Weights, Average Weight, Production, and Mortality Statistics (various culling and mortality rates)
Health & Quality	Health Status indicators, Salmonella serotypes, Hock %, Podo %, Swab, and Sample Details
Nutrition	Comprehensive Feed and Nutrition information

This foundation of over 10,000 data rows provides the necessary context for granular time-series analysis and the development of high-fidelity predictive models across the poultry farming lifecycle.

3.2.3. Methods

The experimental methodology is structured around two primary analytical stages: the statistical confirmation of predictive value and the deployment of advanced machine learning models.

Correlation Analysis

Spearman correlation coefficients were utilized to rigorously quantify the relationship between early-lifecycle indicators (Day 3, Day 7) and final end-cycle outcomes (Day 28). This analysis confirmed the robustness of the selected features as predictors for both weight gain and mortality.

Predictive AI Models

Two distinct machine learning approaches were employed to address the forecasting task:

- **Outlier Detection (MLP Regressor):** An MLP neural network was trained as the primary estimator to solve the binary classification task of identifying high-risk flocks. The model is specifically designed to predict:
 - Flocks falling into the top 10% for late-onset mortality.
 - Flocks falling into the bottom 10% for 28-day weight. The experimental configuration allows for performance prediction at multiple checkpoints (Day 3, Day 7, Day 14, Day 21) to assess the evolution of predictive reliability.
- **Flock Clustering (Time-Series Clustering):** Time-series clustering techniques were applied to group flocks based on the overall shape and trajectory of their daily mortality and weight gain curves. This method is crucial for identifying generalized behavioural patterns and classifying flocks into distinct risk- or performance-profiles early in the lifecycle, enabling **nuanced management** strategies.

3.2.4. Results

The experimentation yielded strong, quantifiable results across both correlation and model performance metrics, confirming the efficacy of early-lifecycle interventions.

Correlation Findings

- **Mortality:** Strong positive correlations were consistently observed. By Day 7, the correlation coefficient was **0.854**, confirming early mortality as a highly robust predictor of long-term flock health.
- **Weight Gain:** The predictive value increased significantly over time. The weak correlation of **0.308 at Day 7** progressed to a strong **0.704 at Day 21**, highlighting the increasing predictive reliability as the growth phase matures.

MLP Outlier Detection Performance

Table 2: Outlier Detection Results for Identifying High-Risk Flocks

Outcome	Predictive Checkpoint	Precision (Few False Positives)	Recall (Identifying High-Risk Flocks)
Mortality (Top 10%)	Day 3	95%	79%
	Day 7	97%	86%
Weight (Bottom 10%)	Day 7	92%	53%
	Day 21	94%	71%

The results show exceptional **Precision** (up to 97%), indicating that the detected high-risk flocks are almost always true outliers. For Mortality, **Recall** improves sharply from 79% to 86% by Day 7, solidifying the model's capability for reliable **early detection**. Weight prediction Recall improves substantially by Day 21, **enhancing the capture rate of underperforming flocks** from just over half to 71%.

Time-Series Clustering Findings

- **Mortality Trajectories:** Clustering analysis revealed distinct, clearly separated clusters early in the lifecycle, enabling confident early assignment of flocks to specific, pre-defined mortality patterns.
- **Weight Trajectories:** Clear separation between top and bottom performers was evident by Day 7. The clustering also provided crucial insights into the **dynamic patterns** within mid-tier performers, where initial trends were observed to shift, validating the need for continuous, data-driven monitoring.

3.2.5. Conclusions

The experimental methodology successfully validated the capability of the **Time Series Prediction Engine** for sophisticated risk assessment in poultry farming. The integration of MLP outlier detection and time-series clustering confirms a significant analytical contribution, transitioning farm management from reactive reporting to **proactive, data-driven intervention**.

The achieved performance metrics - particularly the **97% Precision and 86% Recall for mortality prediction by Day 7** - demonstrate that the models provide highly reliable, actionable insights well before end-cycle outcomes are realized. This work provides poultry farms with a strategic advantage, optimizing efficiency,

ensuring animal welfare, and supporting complex decision-making through objective, categorized flock performance data.

3.3. A Time Series Model for Mycotoxin Risk in Poultry

3.3.1. Summary

This report details the experimental methodology implemented to create a specialized **time series model for mycotoxin risk in poultry**. The objective was to enhance the prediction-engine's capability by providing highly accurate forecasts for poultry-related food safety incidents. The methodology centred on three experimental pillars: **extended data integration** (incorporating poultry feed data), **rigorous algorithm selection** (confirming the suitability of Extra Trees), and **advanced hyperparameter tuning** (increasing the search space to MAX_EVALS=100). The experimental results confirmed that this specialized approach significantly improved the model's capacity to forecast complex trends, particularly those related to feed materials and the mycotoxin hazard.

3.3.2. Data

The experimental foundation for the Mycotoxin Risk model necessitated a significant extension of the standard prediction-engine data framework, aligning with the "Forecasting with Multiple Factors" approach.

Core Time Series: The models utilize the standard monthly aggregated time series, including:

1. Published Incidents (border rejections and recalls).
2. Laboratory Test Results ("above limit" and "below limit").

Extended Domain-Specific Data Integration: To capture nuanced dependencies within the poultry value chain, the engine was extended to incorporate comprehensive historical data specific to **poultry feed**, which serves as a primary input and risk source. This integrated data includes:

- Historical feed contamination incidents.
- Feed ingredient origins.
- Relevant feed production volumes.

This expansion enriches the feature set, allowing the model to leverage a broader array of early indicators of food safety risks that are specific to the poultry farming domain. The standard data sufficiency filters (minimum three years of historical data and 10 individual incidents) were strictly maintained for all trainable time series.

3.3.3. Methods

The experimental methodology applied to the poultry farming models was an intensification of the prediction-engine's existing training and optimization components.

Enhanced Model Training and Algorithm Selection

The model training component underwent an **intensified evaluation process**. An initial experimental stage explored a wider suite of alternative forecasting algorithms and machine learning regressors against the poultry-specific datasets.

- **Conclusion:** Despite the broader algorithmic exploration, the **Extra Trees Regressor** consistently demonstrated **superior performance** and robustness. Its capacity to effectively capture non-linear

relationships and efficiently handle the newly integrated, diverse feature types (including poultry feed data) validated its continued selection as the optimal algorithm for this specialized domain.

Advanced Hyperparameter Tuning

The automated hyperparameter tuning pipeline was executed with an extended scope to ensure that each poultry-specific time series model operates at its peak predictive capability.

- **Optimizer:** Tree of Parzen Estimators (TPE), utilizing the Hyperopt library.
- **Objective:** Minimization of the sMAPE metric.
- **Search Space Expansion:** The parameter was increased from the general model standard of 50 to 100. This expanded search space allowed for a more precise identification of the optimal hyperparameter configurations, crucial for modelling the complex dynamics of mycotoxin risk.

Evaluation and Metrics

Model evaluation utilized the standard rolling window cross-validation scheme. The models remain optimized based on the sMAPE (Symmetric Mean Absolute Percentage Error) objective function to ensure true predictive "closeness" across individual monthly forecasts.

3.3.4. Results

The combined effect of expanded data integration, rigorous algorithm validation, and enhanced hyperparameter tuning resulted in a highly specialized and validated trend forecasting capability.

Empirical Performance: The models successfully demonstrated the capacity to accurately fit historical trends and generate reliable 12-month projections. The refined feature engineering, incorporating feed-specific factors, significantly improved the model's foresight, particularly for low-frequency or high-impact events.

Specific Trend Forecasting Successes:

- **Trend Forecasting for Feed Materials:** The model proved its ability to accurately capture historical trends and project future incident patterns within the complex feed supply chain.
- **Trend Forecasting for Mycotoxin Hazard:** The increased data granularity and expanded tuning search space enabled the model to address highly specific contamination risks, providing **targeted foresight** for critical food safety issues related to the mycotoxin hazard within feed materials.
- **Validation:** The experimental work confirmed the effectiveness of the expanded TPE search space (MAX_EVALS=100) in delivering optimized configurations that consistently minimized sMAPE, thereby maximizing forecasting accuracy and reliability for the poultry domain.

3.3.5. Conclusions

The experimental methodology successfully specialized the prediction-engine for the poultry farming sector. By strategically integrating granular historical poultry feed data and intensifying the hyperparameter tuning process, a highly accurate and robust **time series model for mycotoxin risk** was achieved.

The validation confirms that the chosen algorithm, **Extra Trees Regressor**, remains the optimal choice due to its stability and performance on the expanded, multi-factor dataset. This work delivers a critical tool for proactive risk management, allowing stakeholders to act on highly specialized trend forecasts related to the feed supply chain and specific contaminants like mycotoxins.

3.4. A Mycotoxins Trend Prediction Model for Poultry Feed

3.4.1. Summary

This section describes the preliminary experimental analysis and methodological framework for the **mycotoxins trend prediction model for poultry feed**. The primary motivation is to address the significant impact of mycotoxins on poultry health and production performance using a comprehensive, data-driven approach. This work leverages detailed, long-term sample analysis data from the **Food Fortress** quality assurance scheme. The initial experimental phase focused on preliminary analysis of historical data to identify long-term trends, seasonality, and co-occurrence patterns of key mycotoxins. These foundational insights are critical for informing the design and development of the subsequent **integrated AI Model**, which will correlate mycotoxin fluctuations with internal farm production efficiency and output metrics.

3.4.2. Data

The predictive modelling effort is highly dependent on a unique, comprehensive dataset secured through collaboration with the internationally recognized Food Fortress scheme: <https://www.foodfortress.co.uk>.

Primary Data Source: The dataset comprises **ten years of historical monthly sample analysis data** provided by Food Fortress. This long-term, consistent data collection offers a unique perspective on mycotoxin variability within the feed supply chain.

Data Granularity: The data quantifies the concentration of **four key mycotoxins** per sample:

1. DON
2. Zearalenone
3. Aflatoxin B1
4. Ochratoxin A

Samples are consistently collected and analysed from feed specifically formulated for different animal types (pigs, poultry, and ruminants), allowing for targeted analysis of feed materials relevant to the poultry sector.

Integrated Data for AI Phase (Future): The second phase of the experimental work is designed to integrate the mycotoxin data from the Food Fortress scheme with **Moy Park's internal production data**. This combination will allow the model to investigate the causal and correlational impact of feed quality fluctuations on farm performance metrics (e.g., End-Cycle Weight, Mortality rates).

3.4.3. Methods

The experimental work is divided into two sequential phases, utilizing established time-series and statistical analytical techniques.

Phase 1: Preliminary Analysis Methodology

The initial phase involved a thorough statistical and time-series examination of the Food Fortress dataset to derive foundational knowledge necessary for the AI model design.

1. **Time-Series Decomposition:** The concentration levels of the four key mycotoxins over the ten-year period were subjected to time-series decomposition. This standard analytical technique was used to break down the mycotoxin series into its fundamental components: trend, seasonality, and residual components. This provided a comprehensive understanding of how mycotoxin presence evolves over time.

2. **Co-occurrence Pattern Analysis:** The methodology included detailed analysis to identify patterns of mycotoxin **co-occurrence** within the same feed sample. This involved examining various mycotoxin pairs across different feed types (e.g., Aflatoxin B1 and DON in poultry feed).
3. **Correlation Analysis:** A detailed statistical analysis was performed to identify statistically significant correlations between specific pairs of mycotoxins. This analysis used a significance threshold of $p\text{-value} < 0.05$ to confirm associations that warrant further investigation for their implications on feed safety and animal health.

Phase 2: Integrated AI Model Creation (Subsequent Phase)

This phase, informed by the preliminary analysis, focuses on developing an advanced AI model designed to investigate the direct impact of feed mycotoxin levels on farm production efficiency. The model will leverage the combined feature set of external (Food Fortress) and internal (Moy Park production) data.

3.4.4. Results

The preliminary analysis phase yielded significant empirical insights that are foundational to the subsequent AI model development.

Long-Term Trend Identification

Time-series decomposition successfully identified long-term trends and seasonality within the mycotoxin concentration levels. This decomposition provided a clear overview of the evolution of mycotoxin presence over the decade, crucial for understanding baseline risk variability.

Compelling Co-occurrence Findings

The data exploration revealed compelling insights concerning the co-occurrence of different mycotoxins within the same feed sample. These findings are considered highly significant, potentially advancing the scientific understanding of fungal behaviour in real-world agricultural settings.

Statistically Significant Correlations

The correlation analysis confirmed statistically significant correlations ($p\text{-value} < 0.05$) between specific mycotoxin pairs across various feed types. These validated associations highlight complex interdependencies that must be accounted for by the Integrated AI Model to achieve accurate risk prediction.

3.4.5. Conclusions

The preliminary analysis phase has been successfully completed, providing the necessary foundational element for the Mycotoxins Trend Prediction Model. The thorough examination of the Food Fortress dataset—utilizing time-series decomposition and correlation analysis—has yielded significant and robust insights into the variability, seasonality, and co-occurrence of key mycotoxins.

These confirmed long-term trends, and statistically significant correlations are crucial for designing a high-fidelity AI model. The next phase is now rigorously informed to proceed with the integrated AI model creation, linking external feed quality data directly to internal farm production metrics to achieve targeted management strategies for optimizing poultry farming outcomes. The scientific significance of these preliminary findings also supports a potential scientific publication on mycotoxin co-occurrence.

3.5. Decision Trees for Pest Observation Prediction

3.5.1. Summary

This section describes the preliminary experimental analysis and methodological framework developed for a data-driven, rule-based pest and disease alarm system. The primary motivation is to establish a scientifically grounded, transparent, and adaptive pest alarm framework that can complement or refine existing expert-based systems. More information about the expert pest alarm system can be found in the internal documentation of the AGRIVI Pest Monitoring and Early Warning System.

Traditional pest and disease alarm systems rely heavily on expert knowledge and historical experience. While effective in stable environments, these systems often face challenges in adapting to rapidly changing climatic conditions, emerging pest patterns, and new agricultural practices. To address this limitation, we aim to leverage artificial intelligence (AI), specifically, decision tree algorithms, to automatically extract interpretable decision rules that describe the relationships between key climatic variables and pest or disease occurrences.

3.5.2. Data

The resulting model provides both predictive capability and human-readable rules that can directly inform pest and disease experts. These extracted rules can be used to update, validate, or expand the existing expert alarm system, ensuring it reflects real-world data patterns and is adaptable to changing environmental conditions. This approach thus bridges the gap between data-driven insights and domain expertise, promoting a hybrid framework for climate-smart pest management. The predictive modelling effort is based on a unique and comprehensive dataset acquired through collaboration with AGRIVI, a leading provider of digital farm management platforms.

The dataset comprises historical pest and disease scouting records linked with meteorological observations, expert alarm outputs, and on-field annotations from growers and pest control advisors. Each record represents a combination of weather conditions (temperature, humidity, precipitation) and the corresponding pest or disease occurrence status (alarm = 1, no alarm = 0).

The provided data is split into two parts. First, data from 2024 (n=1713) was used for training, while recent data from 2025 (n=9727) was used to evaluate the resulting models. The climate data include both instantaneous and aggregated indicators: AirTempMin, AirTempMax, AirTempAvg (°C), RelativeHumidityMin, RelativeHumidityMax, RelativeHumidityAvg (%), PrecipAccPeriod (mm over a given period). These variables were selected based on the AGRIVI expert suggestion and their pest alarm system.

The data was aggregated to the daily level, depending on pest observation frequency. Data points from meteorological observations, expert alarm outputs, and on-field annotations from growers and pest control advisors were linked based on location, date, crop type, and pest type. Prior to model training, the dataset was pre-processed, including normalization, handling of missing values, and synchronization of time stamps between pest occurrence data and weather variables.

3.5.3. Methods

The long-term, consistent data collection offers a unique opportunity to understand temporal patterns of pest outbreaks and their dependency on climatic fluctuations, supporting AI model development for both predictive accuracy and interpretability. The methodological goal is to extract interpretable, rule-based relationships between weather variables and pest alarms. To achieve this, we applied a Decision Tree (DT) classifier, a machine learning technique that recursively partitions data into homogenous subsets based on threshold values of predictor variables.

In this case, the model learns decision boundaries under which pest or disease alarms are most likely to trigger. For example, a typical rule extracted from the trained model could be expressed as: *If AirTempMax $\leq 31.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ and PrecipAccPeriod ≤ 1.65 mm and RelativeHumidityMax ≤ 0.8 , then no pest alarm (class 0) Otherwise, if AirTempMax $> 31.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ and RelativeHumidityMax ≥ 0.88 , pest alarm likely (class 1).* Such rules provide explicit and explainable conditions for alarm activation, making them suitable for integration into pest alarm expert systems. Compared with black-box models like neural networks, decision trees maintain high transparency and interpretability, which is essential for acceptance by agricultural practitioners.

The model was trained using a supervised classification approach on labelled pest occurrence data. Separate datasets were used for training (70%), validation (15%), and testing (15%) to ensure robustness. The performance of the trained model was evaluated using standard classification metrics: precision, recall, F1-score, and accuracy.

Further, we applied the trained model to the data 2025 to evaluate the model on new, unseen data.

3.5.4. Results

The decision tree achieved reasonable predictive performance on the held out data set: Validation Performance: Accuracy: 0.71, F1-score (class 1): 0.24, Test Performance: Accuracy: 0.64, F1-score (class 1): 0.20. While the model demonstrates moderate accuracy, especially for the “no alarm” class, it also highlights the challenge of class imbalance, where alarm events (positive cases) are relatively rare. Nevertheless, the decision rules generated provide valuable insight into how climatic conditions influence pest outbreak probabilities. However, recall for alarm events remains low, suggesting that further feature expansion (e.g., lagged climate variables, soil moisture, crop stage) may improve sensitivity.

The trained model applied to the 2025 data, which is newly collected, reached the following performance: Accuracy: 0.84, F1-score (class 1): 0.12. The extracted decision rules form the core of a data-driven knowledge base that can be reviewed and refined by domain experts. These rules describe specific weather thresholds under which pest alarms are likely to occur. For instance, high humidity combined with moderate temperature often corresponds to favourable conditions for fungal diseases.

The goal is to integrate these AI-derived rules into the existing expert pest alarm system, enabling a semi-automated rule update process. This will allow experts to cross-check data-driven rules with empirical knowledge, improving alarm precision and reducing false positives or missed alarms.

3.5.5. Conclusions

This preliminary study demonstrates the feasibility of using interpretable AI methods, specifically decision trees, to derive pest alarm rules from historical weather and observation data. The model captures fundamental relationships between temperature, humidity, and precipitation patterns and pest outbreak occurrences.

Although the current model has moderate accuracy due to limited sample size and class imbalance, it establishes a solid methodological foundation for subsequent iterations. Future work will involve: Expanding the dataset to include more seasons and locations. Comparing multiple interpretable models (e.g., Random Forest, XGBoost with SHAP interpretation).

Validating the extracted rules with pest and disease experts for operational integration. This work marks an essential step toward developing a data-driven, adaptive pest and disease early warning system, enhancing resilience and sustainability in crop protection under changing climatic conditions.

Over the next few years, as more high-quality, well-measured data are accumulated through AGRIVI and other monitoring platforms, the framework can evolve toward a more autonomous and generative AI system.

4. Models Supporting the Greener Efficiency of the EFRA Platform

This chapter reports on experiments concerning models supporting the greener efficiency of the EFRA platform. These include the following:

- An LLM-in-the-loop framework for classification of food risk reports
- Green summarization of regulatory text data
- Effective information retrieval for human-machine interactions
- Efficient early-exit of BERT-based models for ranking
- Efficient multi-vector dense retrieval with bit vectors
- Efficient and effective retrieval over learned representations
- kANNolo: a Rust library for sparse and dense approximate nearest neighbours' search
- Automatic prune binarization

4.1. LLM-in-the-Loop for Classification of Food Risk Reports

4.1.1. Summary

We introduce **Conformal In-Context Learning (CICLe)**, a hybrid framework that combines an efficient base classifier (e.g. traditional machine learning classifiers like Logistic Regression) with a **Large Language Model (LLM)** under the control of a conformal prediction mechanism. Our goal is to address the problem of classifying short, noisy web texts, specifically public food-recall announcements, into many fine-grained categories such as food hazards and product types. These texts are often incomplete, highly domain-specific, and unevenly distributed across classes, which poses major challenges for conventional supervised models. At the same time, relying solely on LLM prompting for every instance is computationally costly and inefficient. CICLe provides a principled solution by using a lightweight base classifier to handle confident predictions, while invoking the LLM when uncertain. This design allows us to combine efficiency with accuracy and to leverage the complementary strengths of symbolic and generative modelling.

Related publication:

- Randl, K., Pavlopoulos, I., Henriksson, A., Lindgren, T. (2024). CICLe: Conformal In-Context Learning for Largescale Multi-Class Food Risk Classification. In Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics (ACL 2024), pp. 7695–7715. DOI: [10.18653/v1/2024.findings-acl.459](https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2024.findings-acl.459).

4.1.2. Data

To support our experiments, we created a new dataset consisting of **7,546 recall announcements** gathered from food safety authorities around the world. Each announcement is annotated at two levels of granularity: one for **hazard categories** such as *Biological*, *Allergen*, or *Chemical Contamination*, or **food product categories** such as *dairy products*, *meat*, or *vegetables* and another with specific **hazards** (e.g. “*listeria monocytogenes*”, “*milk and products thereof*”) and **food products** (e.g. “*mushrooms*”, “*cooked chicken*”). The texts are characteristically short and domain-specific, often containing specialized terminology typical of regulatory reports. The dataset exhibits a high degree of class imbalance, with many categories represented by only a handful of examples. This imbalance makes it a suitable testbed for studying low-resource classification and uncertainty management. The corpus is made publicly available on Zenodo (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10820657](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10820657)) to facilitate reproducible research in this emerging area of food risk communication.

4.1.3. Methods

Our proposed model, CICLE, consists of three main components that together form a hybrid classification pipeline (see **Figure 1** below). First, we train a **base classifier**, in our study a logistic regression model with TF-IDF features, on the labelled training data. This classifier provides probabilistic confidence scores for each class and performs well on frequent or easily separable categories. Second, we calibrate this base classifier for **conformal prediction** using a held-out calibration set. This allows us to leverage the base classifier's estimation of an input text's class probabilities to compute a set of classes that contains the input's correct class with a probability of $1-\alpha$ (α is a parameter chosen at inference time). The conformal layer thus acts as an uncertainty filter that guarantees a controlled error rate. The size of these conformal sets therefore depends on the base classifier's certainty for a given input text: if the base classifier is certain, the predicted conformal set is smaller, if it is uncertain the set gets bigger.

Figure 1: Evaluated Prompting Strategies for Conformal In-Context Learning (CICLE)

In the LLM prompting stage, we query a large language model such as GPT using few-shot in-context learning. Instead of prompting the model with examples from all possible classes, which would be inefficient and error-prone, we include only the classes included in the conformal set. This “reduced prompt” strategy enables the LLM to reason over a focused candidate set, substantially reducing computational cost and improving interpretability. The final prediction for each instance is either the label from the base classifier (when the conformal set is of size one) or the output of the LLM. In this way, CICLE dynamically balances the workload between a fast statistical model and a powerful but expensive language model.

In our experiments, we compare CICLE to three few-shot prompting based baseline strategies: **(i)** The simplest baseline, referred to as **ALL**, uses two few-shot samples per class chosen from the training samples by cosine similarity of TF-IDF embeddings to the input text; **(ii)** In an effort to reduce prompt length for tasks with high numbers of classes, we introduced the **SIM- k** baseline, which includes only the k most similar few-shot samples from the GPT-ALL prompt; **(iii)** As a last baseline, we use **MAX- k** , which is identical to CICLE, but instead of using conformal prediction simply uses the k most probable classes as predicted by the base classifier in the few-shot prompt. For SIM- k we use $k \in \{10, 20\}$ and for MAX- k we use $k \in \{5, 10\}$. All our prompting experiments are using *gpt-3.5-turbo-instruct* as an LLM.

4.1.4. Results

The results of our experiments are shown in **Table 3**. A key advantage of CICLE is its efficiency. Because the LLM is invoked only when the base classifier is uncertain, we were able to reduce the number of LLM calls to between 98% to 60% compared to pure prompting approaches. Moreover, the reduced prompt design limits the number of candidate classes included in each LLM query (we see a reduction in query length of between 69% to 29% compared to the best competitor), further lowering computational cost. Despite these efficiency gains, classification performance remains on par with or better than the strongest baselines. The base classifier alone performs well on frequent classes, while the LLM fallback compensates for difficult or low-resource categories.

Table 3: Results of the LLM Prompting Experiments

Model	F_1 (macro)	LLM usage	Prompt Size (chars)	Classes Per Prompt	Samples Per Class	Failure Rate
hazard-category (10 classes; $\alpha = 0.05$)						
TF-IDF-LR	0.55	–	–	–	–	–
GPT-ALL	0.53	100%	2301.7	10.0	2.0	2%
GPT-SIM-10	0.52	100%	1206.3	5.8	1.7	2%
GPT-MAX-5	0.55	100%	1214.9	5.0	2.0	2%
GPT-SIM-20	0.53	100%	2301.7	10.0	2.0	2%
GPT-MAX-10	0.49	100%	2301.7	10.0	2.0	3%
GPT-CICLE	0.56	60%	707.5	2.6	2.0	2%
product-category (22 classes; $\alpha = 0.05$)						
TF-IDF-LR	0.52	–	–	–	–	–
GPT-ALL	0.72	100%	5621.1	22.0	2.0	2%
GPT-SIM-10	0.66	100%	1378.6	6.6	1.5	4%
GPT-MAX-5	0.64	100%	1395.6	5.0	2.0	4%
GPT-SIM-20	0.69	100%	2614.0	11.6	1.7	2%

GPT-MAX-10	0.68	100%	2631.8	10.0	2.0	6%
GPT-CICLe	0.69	98%	1620.1	5.9	2.0	5%
hazard (102 classes; $\alpha = 0.20$)						
TF-IDF-LR	0.37	–	–	–	–	–
GPT-SIM-10	0.44	100%	1308.0	7.5	1.3	15%
GPT-MAX-5	0.42	100%	1335.4	5.0	2.0	14%
GPT-SIM-20	0.44	100%	2457.0	14.2	1.4	11%
GPT-MAX-10	0.42	100%	2521.1	10.0	2.0	13%
GPT-CICLe	0.42	87%	1251.6	4.7	2.0	14%
product (257 classes; $\alpha = 0.40$)						
TF-IDF-LR	0.54	–	–	–	–	–
GPT-SIM-10	0.54	100%	1238.7	8.5	1.2	34%
GPT-MAX-5	0.56	100%	1270.0	5.0	2.0	20%
GPT-SIM-20	0.53	100%	2324.3	16.7	1.2	36%
GPT-MAX-10	0.57	100%	2385.2	10.0	2.0	23%
GPT-CICLe	0.58	96%	1645.8	6.7	2.0	24%

Through ablation studies, we observed that the conformal significance level (α) provides an effective mechanism for balancing confidence and cost: smaller α values increase accuracy but require more LLM calls, whereas larger α values reduce LLM usage at a modest performance trade-off. Overall, CICLe exhibits stable behaviour across a broad range of α values, confirming that conformal calibration yields robust and interpretable uncertainty control.

4.1.5. Conclusions

In conclusion, CICLe demonstrates that combining calibrated statistical learning with adaptive in-context prompting leads to an efficient and reliable framework for large-scale text classification under uncertainty. By explicitly modelling confidence through conformal prediction, we can decide when to rely on a lightweight model and when to escalate to an LLM, achieving a strong trade-off between accuracy and computational efficiency. The approach is particularly suitable for applications that require continuous monitoring of public information, such as food safety, environmental reporting, or crisis communication, where both interpretability and scalability are essential. Specifically for the EFRA project, this allows fast and efficient tagging of automatically crawled food recall reports, which can be used for early severity estimation (Salmonella contamination is often more problematic than probable contamination with plastic or metal pieces) or categorization.

4.2. Green Summarization of Regulatory Text Data

4.2.1. Summary

This contribution details the development of a methodology for fine-tuning instruction-tuned Large Language Models (LLMs) to achieve effective summarization of regulatory text documents. This model represents a core component of the Information Processing phase within the EFRA platform's Information Retrieval pipeline, primarily supporting Use Case #3, specifically the Automated Regulatory Summarisation Pilot.

Legal text is inherently dense and specialized, making its synthesis a complex task often described as "lossy linguistic compression"—the goal is to condense long documents into digestible summaries without losing critical information. The underlying models developed are fine-tuned versions of open, pre-trained LLMs, with the objective of providing high-quality summaries while emphasizing computational efficiency and sustainability. The development was led by CNR, leveraging regulatory data provided by SGS. The fine-tuned models are publicly accessible on HuggingFace.

Related publications:

- Rocchietti, Guido; Rulli, Cosimo; Randl, Korbinian; Muntean, Cristina Ioana; Nardini, Franco Maria; Perego, Raffaele; Trani, Salvatore; Karvounis, Manos; Janostik, Jakub. *LongDoc Summarization using Instruction-tuned Large Language Models for Food Safety Regulations*. IIR2024: 14th Italian Information Retrieval Workshop, Udine, Italy, 2024.
- Bakagianni, Juli; Randl, Korbinian; Rocchietti, Guido; Rulli, Cosimo; Nardini, Franco Maria; Henriksson, Aron; Trani, Salvatore; Romanova, Anna; Pavlopoulos, John. *FoodSafeSum: Enabling Natural Language Processing Applications for Food Safety Document Summarization and Analysis*. *EMNLP 2025: Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing, China, November 2025*.

4.2.2. Data

The project began by utilizing a preliminary dataset from SGS, consisting of 14,308 HTML documents, of which 9,995 were provided with a summary. A critical observation during the initial phase was that many of the existing scraped summaries were of low quality, often overlapping significantly with the first lines of the HTML content. To overcome this data quality challenge and enhance model robustness, we complemented the SGS data by searching for state-of-the-art external summarization datasets, notably **EUR-Lex-Sum**, which focuses on long-form summarization in the legal domain.

In later, more advanced stages of the project, significant data enhancements were implemented to address the difficulties inherent in processing long regulatory texts.

The corpus was processed into two refined datasets:

1. **SGS-Cut**: Retained only the first 40,000 characters of each document, ensuring input sizes were manageable for the large language models.
2. **SGS-Split**: Documents were segmented into multiple chunks, each limited to 30,000 characters, a technique designed to preserve local context during embedding and retrieval.

These enhanced datasets, along with an extended dataset comprising 137,920 English documents (including 1,987 unique manual summaries), were used to generate **high-quality, silver-standard summaries** for the subsequent fine-tuning of smaller, more resource-efficient models.

4.2.3. Methods

The primary methodology revolved around developing an efficient fine-tuning pipeline for pre-trained LLMs. Several LLMs were initially selected for comparison and fine-tuning, including variants of the Flan-T5 models.

Key methodological steps included:

- **Silver-Standard Generation:** To create high-quality training signals for smaller models, powerful instruction-tuned models, specifically **Llama-3-8B-Instruct** and **CohereForAI Command-R-4bit**, were deployed to generate summaries for the SGS-Cut and SGS-Split datasets.
- **Efficient Fine-tuning:** Smaller, greener models, such as **Google Flan-T5-Large** and the **4-bit quantized Google Gemma-2B**, were then fine-tuned using this synthetic silver-standard data. The 4-bit quantization of Gemma-2B was a deliberate strategy to drastically reduce memory footprint and computational demands, making deployment feasible in resource-constrained environments.
- **Evaluation Metrics:** Evaluation was rigorous, employing standard metrics like **ROUGE-1** (unigram overlap), **ROUGE-L** (longest common subsequence), and **BERTScore** (semantic similarity). Crucially, the domain-specific metric **LongDocFactScore (LDFS)** was added to explicitly evaluate the factual accuracy and consistency of summaries derived from long regulatory texts.
- **Human-in-the-Loop (HITL):** A multi-stage HITL process was integrated, where legal experts from SGS DIGICOMPLY provided iterative evaluation and feedback on the generated summaries, focusing on factual accuracy and legal relevance.

4.2.4. Results

Initial experiments on the small set of manually created summaries demonstrated that the model fine-tuned on the external **EUR-Lex-Sum dataset** achieved the highest Recall. This suggested that the initial SGS data did not effectively enable the model to learn abstractive summarization. Conversely, the model trained on the original SGS scraped data performed optimally when compared against the scraped summaries, as it had learned to extract the first lines of the HTML content, replicating the original data construction method.

The subsequent advanced evaluation phase using the silver-standard training data yielded key results:

- The fine-tuned Flan-T5 model, trained on data generated by CohereForAI, demonstrated **superior performance** across most retrieval metrics.
- The **4-bit quantized Gemma-2B model** successfully achieved a strong balance between model size (computational efficiency) and summarization quality, confirming its viability for sustainable deployment.
- Human evaluation validated that our fine-tuned Flan-T5 models offered **competitive quality** compared to the outputs generated by much larger, proprietary LLMs used internally by SGS, despite being orders of magnitude smaller.

4.2.5. Conclusions

The summarization pipeline provides a robust and practical solution tailored for real-world deployment where computational and energy efficiency is paramount. By strategically employing smaller, fine-tuned models trained using high-quality silver-standard data generated by larger models and validated by human experts, this work directly supports EFRA's objective of enhancing the **sustainability and energy reduction** of the platform's overall AI infrastructure. The fine-tuned models demonstrate a strong operational balance between performance and scalability. Our future steps include applying knowledge distillation techniques and exploring further quantization methods to optimize models for low-resource environments.

4.3. Effective Information Retrieval for Human-Machine Interactions

4.3.1. Summary

This contribution details the development of a **retrieval-augmented chatbot prototype** designed to assist users in interacting with and navigating extensive volumes of food-related regulatory content using natural language queries. The resulting system enables effective regulatory exploration and is integral to Use Case #3, specifically the Smart Regulatory Navigator Pilot. The model relies on Large Language Models to establish **effective retrieval based on dense vector representations**. This work, owned by CNR and supported by data from SGS, establishes the critical retrieval backbone for the interactive components of the EFRA platform. The components, including the models and indexes, are made available on HuggingFace.

Related publication:

- Muntean, Cristina Ioana; Nardini, Franco Maria; Perego, Raffaele; Rocchietti, Guido; Rulli, Cosimo. *Efficient Conversational Search via Topical Locality in Dense Retrieval* (short paper). SIGIR '25, Padua, Italy, 2025. ACM. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3726302.3730186>.

4.3.2. Data

The primary data source utilized is the **SGS dataset of legal documents**. This corpus of regulatory text documents is extensive and complex, necessitating a comprehensive preprocessing step. To prepare the documents for embedding and retrieval, the entire corpus was segmented into manageable text chunks. This chunking strategy ensures that context is adequately preserved within the token limits of the embedding models. Evaluation relies on a **manually curated test set** supplied by SGS DIGICOMPLY, consisting of representative user queries and a corresponding expert-ranked list of relevant document chunks for assessing retrieval effectiveness.

4.3.3. Methods

The methodology implements a standard Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) backend designed for low-latency retrieval.

- **Embedding and Indexing:** Each pre-processed text chunk is converted into a semantic representation using the **Snowflake embedding model**. To facilitate efficient retrieval at scale, a vector index was constructed using **FAISS (Facebook AI Similarity Search)**. This mechanism allows for fast Approximate Nearest Neighbor (ANN) search over large embedding datasets, which is crucial for real-time chatbot responsiveness.
- **Query Processing:** User queries are also embedded using the Snowflake model, and the retrieval system fetches the semantically closest document chunks from the FAISS index.
- **Evaluation Challenges and Refinement:** Initial challenges were encountered during the evaluation process due to the nature of the human-curated ground truth, where relevant chunks were duplicated across multiple documents. To ensure robust benchmarking, post-processing was implemented to match labelled chunks against the full dataset and identify all instances of relevant content. Furthermore, the indexing process was refined to assign a unique identifier to each distinct chunk of text within the index, enabling accurate measurement of retrieval accuracy, precision at rank, recall, and Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR).

4.3.4. Results

The current focus is on executing a systematic and robust evaluation of the retrieval performance using the human-curated test set provided by SGS. This benchmarking process is designed to measure the model's ability to accurately retrieve highly relevant documents and detect any potential retrieval errors or shifts in semantic embedding performance.

4.3.5. Conclusions

This retrieval methodology successfully delivers the essential **backbone for effective regulatory exploration and user interaction** within the EFRA platform. It will be directly integrated into a full chatbot interface, enabling real-time responses to natural language queries, often complemented by the retrieval-grounded summarization capabilities of the other models. Future work will concentrate on optimizing key system parameters, including the fine-tuning of document chunking strategies, validating embedding model performance, and refining the FAISS index configuration to maximize top-k accuracy.

4.4. Efficient Early-Exit of BERT-based Models for Ranking

4.4.1. Summary

This activity addresses the high computational cost associated with deep neural networks derived from Large Language Models (LLMs) when used for document ranking in Information Retrieval (IR) scenarios. These complex models, often employed in the **Precision-oriented Ranking phase** to refine initial retrieval results, are computationally intensive. To enhance sustainability and energy efficiency, this work introduces the **Similarity-based Early Exit (SEE)** strategy.

SEE is a novel, non-learned approach that leverages similarities found between query and document token embeddings within BERT-based models (such as MonoBERT, MonoELECTRA, and MonoRoBERTa) to preemptively terminate the inference process for documents highly likely to be non-relevant. By significantly reducing the computational load during the re-ranking step, SEE directly supports the development of greener modules for the EFRA Platform. This CNR contribution is applicable to both the Automated Regulatory Summarisation Pilot and the Smart Regulatory Navigator Pilot within Use Case #3. The source code is publicly available.

Related publication:

- F. Busolin, C. Lucchese, F. M. Nardini, S. Orlando, R. Perego, S. Trani, and A. Veneri, "Efficient Re-ranking with Cross-encoders via Early Exit," in ACM SIGIR 2025. doi: [10.1145/3726302.3729962](https://doi.org/10.1145/3726302.3729962).

4.4.2. Data

The SEE model operates on Query and document content provided as text.

- **Training Data:** To establish the foundational MonoX ranking models, finetuning was conducted on the Microsoft Machine Reading Comprehension (**MS-MARCO**) dataset and a ranking-adapted version of the Answer-Sentence Natural Questions (**ASNQ**) dataset.
- **Evaluation Data:** The methodology was rigorously evaluated using standard information retrieval benchmarks: the **TREC Deep Learning Track 2019 and 2020 editions** (trec-dl-2019 and trec-dl-2020), in addition to a subset of ASNQ queries.

4.4.3. Methods

SEE is distinguished from existing learned early exit methods because it is a **non-learned strategy**, meaning it does not require an additional training phase to determine the exit condition.

- **Architecture and Placement:** The core idea is based on the hypothesis that token representations can predict the final document score. A singular early exit filter is placed before a designated transformer block, most effectively implemented **before the first transformer block** to minimize computational cost.
- **Similarity Proxies:** Four distinct similarity measures (Max, MeanSim, CentrSim, MaxSim) were investigated as proxies to estimate the final ranking score between a query and document token embeddings
- **Listwise Exit Strategies:** Unlike learned approaches that make pointwise decisions (per query-document pair), SEE uses listwise strategies. Three solutions were implemented: Exit by Similarity Threshold (EST), Exit by Rank Threshold (ERT), and Exit by Proximity Threshold (EPT). EPT extends ERT by filtering documents whose similarity is within a certain proximity of the similarity score of the document at rank k , ensuring that only the most highly relevant candidates proceed.
- **Implementation Efficiency:** To maximize GPU utilization, the implementation partitions the original MonoX model into two slices around the filter. This innovative approach requires only a single, query-wise rebatching step, which is significantly more efficient than previous learned strategies that necessitate rebatching after every single transformer block. Performance was evaluated using nDCG@10 for effectiveness and estimating both estimated speedup and real speedup.

4.4.4. Results

The experimental evaluation demonstrated substantial gains in efficiency:

- **Estimated Speedup:** When compared to the baseline eeMB, SEE consistently achieved superior effectiveness (higher nDCG@10) on the trec-dl-2019 dataset.
- **MonoELECTRA Performance:** The most disruptive performance was observed when applying SEE using the EPT strategy to the **MonoELECTRA** model on the trec-dl-2020 dataset, achieving a high average real speedup of approximately **4.9x**, while incurring a minimal loss in nDCG@10 (3.3% relative loss).
- **MonoBERT Performance:** SEE-MonoBERT also performed strongly, achieving a real speedup of **3.93x** on the trec-dl-2019 dataset.
- **Comparison to Baselines:** The real speedups achieved by SEE (e.g., 4.90x for MonoELECTRA) were significantly higher than those achieved by the optimized learned baseline (eeMB+, which peaked around 2.64x). This superior efficiency is directly attributable to the design of SEE, which requires only one re-batching step compared to the multiple re-batching steps required by learned classifiers, minimizing computational overhead.

4.4.5. Conclusions

The Similarity-based Early Exit (SEE) strategy is an extremely powerful and efficient methodology that directly contributes to enhancing the **sustainability and efficiency of neural ranking models**. By achieving high speedups (up to 4.9x) with minimal sacrifice in retrieval effectiveness, SEE significantly reduces the computational cost and inference time required for the precision-oriented ranking phase within the EFRA Information Retrieval pipeline. A key benefit for deployment is that SEE is easy to implement and does not require the costly retraining phase necessary for learned early exit strategies. Future research efforts will focus on further optimizing the GPU implementation for even higher real speedups and exploring the use of multiple similarity filters.

4.5. Efficient Multi-Vector Dense Retrieval with Bit Vectors

4.5.1. Summary

This activity tackles the problem of efficient retrieval over learned multi-vector representations. **Multi-vector representations** are a family of embeddings where a transformer-based neural architecture is used to produce a contextualized vector for documents and queries. This paradigm provides for higher effectiveness compared to the more common single-vector one, at the price of higher resource consumption, in terms of memory, energy consumption, and query processing time.

Efficient Multi-Vector Retrieval with Bit Vectors (EMVB) is a novel technique that allows for efficient retrieval over multi-vector representations. At the indexing phase, EMVB builds a set of centroids over the entire - possibly very large - term vector collection and then stores each vector using the centroid identifier and a compressed version of the residual. During query processing, EMVB quickly determines the candidate documents by approximating the similarity between the query and a document with the similarity between the query and the centroids associated with each term in the document. Compared to previous approaches, EMVB uses a bit vector to quickly discard non-relevant documents. EMVB allows for faster and **more energy-efficient** retrieval over multi-vector representations and can be applied to any use case requiring highly effective and efficient retrieval, such as the Automated Regulatory Summarisation Pilot and the Smart Regulatory Navigator Pilot within Use Case #3. The source [code](#) is publicly available.

Related publication:

- F. M. Nardini, C. Rulli, and R. Venturini, "Efficient Multi-vector Dense Retrieval with Bit Vectors," in *Advances in Information Retrieval - ECIR 2024*. doi: [10.1007/978-3-031-56060-6_1](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-56060-6_1).

4.5.2. Data

The effectiveness of EMVB is evaluated on two benchmarks:

- **MS-MARCO** MicroSoft MACHine Reading COMprehension, a collection of 8.8 million passages with about 7k queries for evaluation (*dev.small* set)
- **LOTTE** Pooled Dataset, a dataset for long-context information retrieval combining five domain-specific datasets derived from StackExchange: Writing, Recreation, Science, Technology, and Lifestyle, with 2.6 million documents.

4.5.3. Methods

The main technical contributions of EMVB are

- **Bit Vectors.** EMVB introduces an innovative pre-filtering mechanism based on optimized bit vectors that efficiently identifies and discards non-relevant passages during candidate selection. The bit vector representation maps centroid identifiers into compact binary arrays where membership testing can be performed in constant time through bitwise operations.
- **Product Quantization.** EMVB employs Product Quantization (PQ), enabling efficient compression of residual vectors while allowing direct computation of dot products without requiring decompression. The framework uses JMPQ (Joint optimization of Multi-vector representation with Product Quantization) for in-domain scenarios, which optimizes the quantization codes during the language model's fine-tuning phase, and OPQ (Optimized Product Quantization) for out-of-domain evaluation (where no training queries are at disposal), which finds an optimal rotation of vectors to minimize quality degradation.

- **Efficient implementation.** EMVB is implemented in C++ with a strong focus on leveraging modern CPU architectures to achieve maximum performance through low-level optimizations. The framework extensively exploits SIMD (Single Instruction, Multiple Data) instructions, particularly AVX512, to perform vectorized operations on 512-bit registers, enabling parallel processing of multiple values simultaneously. To avoid the performance penalties associated with branch misprediction, EMVB implements branchless algorithms that eliminate conditional branches from critical code paths.

4.5.4. Results

Our extensive evaluation on MS-MARCO and LoTTE datasets shows that, compared to the state-of-the-art competitor PLAID (at the time of publication)

- **MS-MARCO** dataset (in-domain). EMVB can achieve up to 2.8× speedup compared to PLAID while reducing memory footprint by 1.8× with no loss in retrieval effectiveness. Increasing the memory budget—from 20 to 36 bytes per vector—EMVB achieves up to 2.5× speedup with the same memory footprint as PLAID and delivers superior effectiveness.
- **LoTTE** dataset (out-of-domain). EMVB achieves even greater speedups of up to 2.9× compared to PLAID, with minimal quality degradation. The larger speedups on LoTTE are attributed to the dataset's longer average document lengths, where the bit vector-based pre-filtering has a more substantial impact on reducing the number of candidate passages that need to be processed in subsequent phases.

4.5.5. Conclusions

EMVB is a novel framework that significantly advances the state-of-the-art in efficient multi-vector dense retrieval. Experimental evaluation on MS MARCO and LoTTE datasets demonstrates that EMVB delivers substantial performance improvements over PLAID, the previous state-of-the-art system. On MS MARCO, EMVB achieves up to 2.8× speedup and 1.8× memory reduction with no loss in retrieval quality. On LoTTE, EMVB provides up to 2.9× speedup with minimal quality degradation. These results are achieved through careful implementation in C++, leveraging SIMD instructions and branchless algorithms, demonstrating that multi-vector dense retrieval systems can be made practical for real-world deployment without sacrificing effectiveness. EMVB can be employed both in the first, recall-oriented stage of any of the EFRA Pipeline, or it can be used as a cheap, GPU-less reranker to prune the final candidate list fed to a reranker.

4.6. Efficient and Effective Retrieval over Learned Representations

4.6.1. Summary

This activity addresses the challenge of efficient retrieval over learned sparse representations. Learned sparse representations are a family of contextual embeddings for text retrieval that are effective models of relevance and interpretable by design. Similar to dense vectors (both single-vector and multi-vector), sparse vectors are produced by a transformer-based neural architecture. Yet, instead of producing representations projected in the latent space of the neural model, sparse embeddings are grounded on the token vocabulary.

Seismic (Spilled Clustering of Inverted Lists with Summaries for Maximum Inner Product Search) is a framework that introduces a novel organization of the inverted index by partitioning inverted lists into geometrically-cohesive blocks, each equipped with a summary vector. During query processing, Seismic quickly determines if a block must be evaluated using the summaries, significantly reducing computational

costs. The design uses two familiar data structures in innovative ways: the inverted index for identifying candidate documents and the forward index for computing exact inner products. Building on the original Seismic framework, two important extensions have been developed: first, ordered block traversal and augmenting the index with a κ -NN graph to achieve near-exact accuracy levels. Second, a comprehensive scalability study on massive datasets (138M documents) demonstrates that Seismic maintains its efficiency advantages even at extreme scales, with sub-3-millisecond query latency at 98% accuracy.

Seismic can be applied to any use case requiring highly effective and efficient retrieval over sparse representations, such as document search, question answering, and information retrieval tasks. The source [code](#) is publicly available.

Related publications:

- S. Bruch, F. M. Nardini, C. Rulli, and R. Venturini, "Efficient Inverted Indexes for Approximate Retrieval over Learned Sparse Representations," SIGIR 2024 doi: [10.1145/3626772.3657769](https://doi.org/10.1145/3626772.3657769).
- S. Bruch, F. M. Nardini, C. Rulli, and R. Venturini, "Pairing Clustered Inverted Indexes with κ -NN Graphs for Fast Approximate Retrieval over Learned Sparse Representations," CIKM 2024 doi: [10.1145/3627673.3679977](https://doi.org/10.1145/3627673.3679977).
- S. Bruch, F. M. Nardini, C. Rulli, R. Venturini, and L. Venuta, "Investigating the Scalability of Approximate Sparse Retrieval Algorithms to Massive Datasets," ECIR 2025 doi: [10.1007/978-3-031-88714-7_43](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-88714-7_43).

4.6.2. Data

The effectiveness of Seismic is evaluated on two benchmarks:

- **MS-MARCO** MicroSoft MACHine Reading COmprehension, a collection of 8.8 million passages with about 7k queries for evaluation (*dev.small* set)
- **Natural Questions** (NQ) from BEIR: A collection of 2.68 million questions in English with 7,842 test queries, used for out-of-domain evaluation.
- **MS-MARCO v2**: A significantly larger collection of 138 million passages with 3,903 queries in the dev1 set, used to evaluate scalability to massive datasets.

The framework is evaluated using embeddings from three learned sparse representations (LSR) models. All these models produce embeddings in the BERT vocabulary (WordPiece), which conceives about 30k terms:

- **Splade**: This module produces document embeddings with an average of 119 non-zero entries in documents and 43 non-zero entries for queries - stats computed on the MS MARCO dataset.
- **Efficient Splade (E-Splade)**: This module produces document embeddings with an average of 181 non-zero entries in documents and 5.9 non-zero entries for queries - stats computed on the MS MARCO dataset.
- **Splade-v3**: An improved variant incorporating a modified objective and distillation strategy, with an average of 168 (24) non-zero entries in documents (queries) for MS MARCO.
- **uniCoil-T5**: This module produces document embeddings with an average of 60 non-zero entries in documents and 6 non-zero entries for queries - stats computed on the MS MARCO dataset.

4.6.3. Methods

We list the main technical contributions of Seismic.

- **Geometrically-Cohesive Blocking:** Seismic introduces a novel blocking strategy that partitions each inverted list into β blocks using a clustering algorithm. This groups together documents that are similar in their local representations, facilitating efficient dynamic pruning during query processing.
- **Per-block Summary Vectors:** Each block is equipped with a summary vector—a compressed representation that approximates the inner product between a query and the documents within the block. Summary vectors are built by taking the maximum value of each coordinate among documents in the block, then pruning to keep only the α -mass subvector (the top entries that preserve a fraction α of the L_1 mass). Scalar quantization (8-bit) is applied to further reduce the memory footprint while maintaining effectiveness.
- **Static Pruning:** For each coordinate, Seismic builds its inverted list by gathering all documents with non-zero values, sorting them by value in decreasing order, and pruning to keep at most the top λ entries. This leverages the "concentration of importance" property observed in learned sparse embeddings, where a small subset of the most important coordinates effectively approximates the full inner product.
- **Ordered Block Traversal (OBT) and κ -NN Graph Expansion.** Rather than visiting blocks within inverted lists in arbitrary order, we sort blocks by their summary score (inner product with the query) in descending order. This ensures that the most promising blocks are evaluated first. Moreover, we augment the index with a κ -regular nearest neighbour graph where each document is connected to its κ nearest neighbours. After the initial retrieval, the system expands the candidate set by including neighbours of retrieved documents.

4.6.4. Results

Our extensive evaluation on MS MARCO and Natural Questions datasets shows that Seismic is the state-of-the-art strategy for retrieving over learned sparse representations, as it outperforms all competitors across all evaluated benchmarks.

- **MS MARCO dataset (in-domain):** Seismic outperforms the winners of the NeurIPS BigANN Challenge (Sparse Track), being up to 3.6x, 21.6x, and 22.6x on Splade, E-Splade, and UniCoil, respectively.
- **Natural Questions dataset (out-of-domain):** Seismic confirms its efficiency on out-of-domain use cases, being up to 5.1x times faster.
- **Index size and build time:** On Splade embeddings of MS MARCO, Seismic's index requires 6,416 MiB and can be built in just 5 minutes using 64 cores, significantly faster than GrassRMA (267 minutes) and PyAnn (137 minutes), i.e., the winner of the NeurIPS BigANN Challenge.
- **OBT and κ -NN Graph.** We can achieve speedups of up to 2.2x over base Seismic, on Spladev3 embeddings. The benefits of these additional features are evident in near-exact search scenarios.
- **MS MARCO-v2 dataset (138M documents):** Seismic demonstrates remarkable scalability on massive datasets, processing queries with sub-3-millisecond latency at 98% accuracy while being 6.9x faster than HNSW. Index construction is 25x faster than competing graph-based approaches. Despite the dataset being 15x larger than MS MARCO v1, Seismic experiences less than 8x slowdown, demonstrating favourable scaling laws and confirming its practical applicability to real-world large-scale retrieval scenarios.

4.6.5. Conclusions

Seismic is a novel approximate nearest neighbour algorithm that significantly advances the state-of-the-art in efficient retrieval over learned sparse representations. Experimental evaluation on MS MARCO and Natural

Questions demonstrates that Seismic delivers substantial performance improvements over existing solutions, including state-of-the-art graph-based and inverted index-based methods.

Seismic is a superluminal retrieval engine that allows for sub-3-millis latency on almost 140 million documents. It can be used to quickly find candidate documents in extremely large knowledge bases, including any data source of the EFRA project or even larger ones, like the Wikipedia collection. Any use cases entailing an efficient yet effective retrieval benefit from Seismic.

4.7. kANNolo: Rust Library for Sparse and Dense Approximate Nearest Neighbours Search

4.7.1. Summary

This contribution addresses the need for a flexible, modular, and high-performance library for Approximate Nearest Neighbours (ANN) search. Current state-of-the-art ANN libraries, although performance-oriented, often lack modularity and ease of use, making them unsuitable for easy prototyping and testing of research ideas. What the landscape of ANN was missing was a tool to allow practitioners to quickly test and develop ideas, or to adapt existing solutions to specific use cases with minimal effort.

kANNolo is a novel research-oriented ANN library written in Rust and explicitly designed to combine usability with performance effectively. Unlike existing libraries, kANNolo is the first ANN library that supports both dense and sparse vector representations on top of different similarity measures (e.g., Euclidean distance and inner product) and vector quantization techniques (e.g., Product Quantization). The source code is publicly available on GitHub.

kANNolo represents a crucial advancement for adapting state-of-the-art retrieval solutions to specific EFRA use cases. By natively supporting dense, sparse, and multi-vector representations, kANNolo provides flexibility in integrating cutting-edge embeddings into any use case that may require them. The ability to seamlessly switch between different representation types and similarity measures allows practitioners to quickly identify the optimal configuration for their specific retrieval tasks, significantly accelerating the development cycle from experimentation to deployment.

Related publication:

- Delfino, D. Erriquez, S. Martinico, F. M. Nardini, C. Rulli, and R. Venturini, "kANNolo: Sweet and Smooth Approximate k-Nearest Neighbors Search," ECIR 2025. doi: [10.1007/978-3-031-88717-8_29](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-88717-8_29).

4.7.2. Data

The effectiveness of kANNolo is evaluated on multiple benchmarks covering both dense and sparse representations:

- Dense datasets:
 - **Sift1M**: A widely-known dataset consisting of 1 million vectors of handcrafted visual descriptors of images with 128 dimensions, evaluated using Euclidean distance (L2).
 - **MS MARCO** (MicroSoft MACHine Reading COMprehension) with Star embeddings: 8.8 million passages embedded with the Star model, producing 768-dimensional dense vectors evaluated using inner product.
 - **MS MARCO** with Dragon embeddings: 8.8 million passages embedded with the Dragon model, producing 768-dimensional dense vectors evaluated using inner product.
- Sparse dataset:

- **MS MARCO** with Splade embeddings: 8.8 million passages embedded with the Splade model, producing sparse representations in the BERT WordPiece vocabulary (approximately 30,000 terms), evaluated using inner product.

4.7.3. Methods

The main technical contributions of kANNolo are:

- **Modular Architecture with Rust Traits:** kANNolo is built with four main abstract components managed through Rust traits (a mechanism for specifying shared behaviour across types). This design allows users to easily develop and integrate new indices and quantizers with minimal effort.
- **HNSW Graph Index:** The indexing method currently implemented in kANNolo is the Hierarchical Navigable Small World (HNSW) graph, a state-of-the-art method that has proven to be effective for both dense and sparse retrieval.
- **Product Quantization:** kANNolo implements Product Quantization (PQ), which quantizes high-dimensional data into more compact representations by partitioning vectors into subspaces and quantizing each subspace independently.
- **Unified Interface for Dense and Sparse Data:** Unlike competitors that require specialized implementations for different vector types, kANNolo operates the same indexing algorithm independently of the vector representation (dense or sparse), quantizer, and similarity measure used, enabling seamless experimentation across different configurations.

4.7.4. Results

Our evaluation shows that kANNolo achieves both modularity and state-of-the-art performance:

- **Dense datasets:** On Sift1M, kANNolo is competitive with state-of-the-art libraries (FAISS, hnsplib, N2). On MS MARCO with Star and Dragon embeddings, kANNolo outperforms all competitors, achieving up to 11.1× speedup over FAISS, when using HNSW in combination with Product Quantization.
- **Sparse dataset:** On MS MARCO with Splade embeddings, kANNolo outperforms both GrassRMA and PyAnn (the winning submissions of the NeurIPS 2023 BigANN Challenge Sparse Track), achieving up to 2.1× speedup while maintaining comparable or better accuracy.
- **Modularity:** All tests on both sparse and dense datasets, with and without quantization, were conducted using the same indexing algorithm and codebase, which shows the flexibility of the method.

4.7.5. Conclusions

kANNolo is a novel Rust-based library for approximate nearest neighbours' search designed to ease the prototyping and development of new ANN algorithms. The benchmarking on several public dense and sparse datasets demonstrates that kANNolo achieves genuine modularity through its trait-based architecture while also delivering state-of-the-art performance against well-known competitors. These results confirm that kANNolo is a valuable tool for effectively advancing ANN research, providing researchers with a flexible experimental playground that does not compromise on efficiency. Future work includes extending kANNolo with additional indexing methods (such as inverted indexes) and quantization techniques to provide researchers with an even broader experimental toolkit.

4.8. Automatic Prune Binarization

4.8.1. Summary

This contribution presents a model compression strategy named Automatic Prune Binarization (APB), designed to enhance the energy efficiency and deployability of deep neural networks within the EFRA platform. APB integrates pruning and binarization directly into the training phase of a model, rather than treating them as decoupled post-training optimizations. The core idea is to represent most network weights using 1-bit binarized values, while automatically retaining only a tiny fraction of full-precision weights to preserve expressiveness and avoid accuracy degradation. To achieve this, APB introduces a learned binarization interval around zero: weights falling inside this interval are binarized to $\pm\alpha$ (with α being a trainable scaling factor), whereas weights outside are kept in standard floating-point precision. This approach yields extremely compact, computationally efficient models while maintaining accuracy levels suitable for EFRA analytics and risk prediction scenarios.

Related publication:

- Nardini, F. M., Rulli, C., Trani, S., & Venturini, R. (2025). Neural network compression using binarization and few full-precision weights. *Information Sciences*, 716, 122251. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2025.122251>

4.8.2. Data

The evaluation of APB was conducted on well-established image classification datasets commonly adopted for benchmarking lightweight and efficient model architectures:

- **CIFAR-10** and **CIFAR-100**, used to study compression impact on mid-scale classification tasks.
- **ImageNet**, used to assess scalability and generalization under large-scale, higher-dimensional conditions.

Datasets were processed using standard training and validation splits and common data augmentation techniques. To reflect EFRA's focus on constrained computing scenarios, additional tests were performed using reduced subsets simulating limited-resource inference conditions similar to edge deployments or low-bandwidth data nodes.

4.8.3. Methods

APB modifies the standard forward and backward computation of a neural network as follows:

- During training, each weight is evaluated against a **dynamic threshold** defining the binarization interval.
- Weights inside the interval are mapped to a binary representation ($\pm\alpha$), minimizing memory size and arithmetic complexity.
- Only a **small proportion of weights with higher magnitude** are retained in full precision to preserve learning capacity.
- Inference is executed through two combined operations:
 - **Fast binary matrix multiplications**, leveraging bitwise operations for high throughput.
 - **Sparse full-precision operations**, limited to the retained subset of weights.

This dual representation allows APB models to behave similarly to fully binarized networks in terms of speed and memory usage, while preserving accuracy levels closer to full-precision models.

4.8.4. Results

Experiments demonstrate that:

- APB achieves **significant memory reduction** (over 90% compared to the full-precision baseline).
- **Inference throughput increases up to 2×** compared to low-bit quantization approaches using 2-bit weights, especially on CPU architectures without specialized accelerators.
- **Accuracy remains close to full-precision performance**, particularly when retaining as little as 5% full-precision weights.
- Under aggressive compression settings, APB exhibits **more stable degradation patterns** than pruning-only or quantization-only techniques, preserving robustness in low-resource EFRA deployment scenarios.

These results confirm that APB enables faster, lighter, and energy-aware execution, aligned with EFRA's platform constraints.

4.8.5. Conclusions

APB provides a practical methodology for embedding efficiency into the model lifecycle, making it suitable for real deployment within the EFRA platform, where energy constraints, distributed inference, and scalable model deployment are key operational requirements. By reducing model size and computational intensity, APB facilitates:

- Lower energy consumption during inference,
- Faster model serving on EFRA edge and cloud nodes,
- Better integration with EFRA's green scheduling and orchestration policies.

In future iterations, the APB technique can be extended beyond vision models, including transformer-based architectures for regulatory text analysis or anomaly detection, further contributing to the sustainability and computational efficiency goals of EFRA.

5. Other Models for the EFRA Platform

This chapter reports on experiments concerning other models for the EFRA platform. They include the following:

- Self-counterfactual explanations for text classification
- A shared task on food recall classification (SemEval 2025)
- EFRA conceptual model annotator for food recall classification

5.1. Self-Counterfactual Explanations for Text Classification

5.1.1. Summary

In our study, we investigate how LLMs generate and justify their own predictions through self-explanations. Self-explanations are a recently proposed rationale based explainability method, where the LLM is prompted to justify its own output after few-shot prompting. Our main objective is to assess whether these explanations genuinely reflect the model's internal reasoning or merely appear convincing to human evaluators. In line with Agarwal et al. (Faithfulness versus plausibility: On the (Un)reliability of explanations from large language models. 2024. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2402.04614](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2402.04614)), we identify a critical distinction between **plausibility**, which concerns human-perceived reasonableness, and **faithfulness**, which concerns factual correspondence to the model's actual decision process. To bridge this gap, we introduce a method for generating **valid counterfactual self-explanations**, i.e. instances where the model itself produces and verifies alternative inputs that cause its predicted label to change. Our work contributes new procedures to ensure explanation validity and provides adaptations of analytic interpretability techniques, such as gradient- and attention-based saliency, for use with autoregressive LLMs.

Related publication:

- Randl, K., Pavlopoulos, J., Henriksson, A., Lindgren, T. Mind the Gap: From Plausible to Valid Self-Explanations in Large Language Models. *Machine Learning*, 114, 220 (2025). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10994-025-06838-6>.

5.1.2. Data

We evaluate our methods across three representative classification datasets chosen to cover diverse interpretability contexts: a **food-hazard detection** dataset developed in the course of the EFRA project with well-defined, objectively labelled short texts (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10820657](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10820657)); a **sentiment classification** corpus reflecting subjective reasoning patterns; and a **toxicity detection** dataset addressing socially sensitive content. Each dataset includes human-annotated rationales that serve as gold-standard references for evaluating the plausibility and precision of model explanations. By combining subjective and objective domains, we can probe explanation validity under varying linguistic ambiguity and task complexity.

5.1.3. Methods

Our methodology distinguishes two complementary forms of self-explanation. In **extractive self-explanation**, the model is prompted to highlight the specific words or phrases that most influenced its prediction (see **Table 4** below). In **counterfactual self-explanation**, the model proposes a minimally modified version of the input that would lead to a different classification. To benchmark the interpretive quality of these self-explanations, we compare them against established analytic approaches, including attention-based and gradient-based saliency maps as well as SHAP, a model-agnostic baseline.

Table 4: Example of a Chat Sequence

(a) **User:** What is the sentiment of the following review?

“Hints are made to the audience that this film could be a blast. Alas, these are only hints.”

Assign one of the following labels: “negative” or “positive”. Make sure to answer only with the label or "none" if none of them applies.

llm: Negative

(b) **user:** What is the most important phrase influencing your assessment? Provide only the phrase as a string.

llm: “Alas, these are only hints.”

(c) **user:** Provide a version of the announcement that would alter your assessment to "positive" while changing as few words in the original announcement as possible. Make sure to only answer with the changed announcement.

llm: “Hints are made to the audience that this film could be a blast. And indeed, these are more than just hints.”

A central methodological contribution is our **validity-sampling strategy**, shown in the figure below. Specifically, candidate counterfactuals are generated at high temperature and subsequently verified by the model itself to ensure that the modified input indeed changes the predicted label. This allows us to compute the expected number of samples required to obtain a valid counterfactual, thereby replacing ad-hoc heuristics with a statistically grounded criterion.

Figure 2: Workflow for Generating Valid Counterfactual Self-Explanations

We further propose refinements for computing gradient-based explanations in autoregressive contexts, including noise filtering and token-level aggregation schemes that address multi-token label outputs.

5.1.4. Results

Our results demonstrate that while large language models frequently produce **plausible explanations** that align with human expectations, these are not necessarily **faithful** to the model’s internal decision process. We quantify this discrepancy through correlation analyses between self-explanations, human rationales, and analytic attribution maps. Without validity checks, many counterfactual explanations turn out to be invalid: the model’s prediction remains unchanged despite input alterations. As shown in **Figure 3** below, our experiments reveal that achieving full validity of counterfactual self-explanations is feasible but highly dependent on both model architecture and task complexity. While 100% validity can be reached within ten sampling attempts ($k=10$), the best counterfactuals typically emerge at lower k values, as validity plateaus early. Model size or family does not show a consistent influence on this ability: for instance, only **Llama 3.1-70B** achieves 100% valid counterfactuals in the first two tasks, yet nearly all models except **Gemma 2.0** and **Llama 3.2** reach at least 90% validity in those same tasks. In contrast, performance on the more challenging third task declines: first-try validity drops noticeably, even though the generated counterfactuals remain semantically like the originals. This suggests that cfSE validity is closely tied to the model’s conceptual grasp of the underlying task.

Across all models, both **validity** and the **prediction probability** $p(\text{LLM}(cf)=\hat{y}_{cf})$ for the target class stabilize after roughly two sampling attempts, with further increases in k offering negligible improvements in similarity or ROUGE scores. Larger models consistently outperform smaller ones of the same family, producing more valid, coherent, and semantically faithful counterfactuals, confirming that model capacity enhances reliability in complex reasoning and explanation generation.

Figure 3: Results of Experiments for Creating Valid Self-Counterfactuals

5.1.5. Conclusions

Through this work, we establish a reproducible and transparent experimental framework for evaluating self-explanation validity in LLMs. Our results highlight that plausibility alone is insufficient as an interpretability criterion and that faithful, verifiable explanation generation requires methodological rigor in both experimental design and computational tooling. The corresponding implementation and datasets are made publicly available to foster replication and extension of our findings. In the EFRA project, we use the explored method in combination with the CICLE classifier to create a transparent pipeline for early tagging of food recall texts.

5.2. Shared Task on Food Recall Classification

5.2.1. Summary

In the SemEval-2025 Food Hazard Detection challenge, we explored classification of web texts reporting food incidents under severe long-tail class distributions. The challenge was organized into two subtasks: **Subtask 1 (ST1, coarse classification of hazard category and product category)** and **Subtask 2 (ST2, fine-grained “vector” classification, i.e. directly predicting the specific hazard and product)**. For the purposes of this challenge, we extended the food recall incidents dataset to 6,644 manually labelled reports, publicly released on Zenodo under CC BY-NC-SA 4.0(DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10820657](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10820657)). Our analysis emphasizes that LLM-generated synthetic data is effective for oversampling the underrepresented classes, and that multiple transformer architectures (encoder-only, encoder-decoder, decoder-only) reach comparable top performance. We also provide a broad survey of participating systems, describe winning strategies, and analyse sources of error and task difficulty.

Related publication:

- Randl, K., Pavlopoulos, J., Henriksson, A., Lindgren, T., Bakagianni, J. (2025). SemEval-2025 Task 9: The Food Hazard Detection Challenge. In Proceedings of the 19th International Workshop on Semantic Evaluation (SemEval 2025).

5.2.2. Data

The new version of the dataset consists of 6,644 records, each comprising a **TITLE** (average ~88 characters) and a **TEXT** body (average length ~2,329 characters), drawn from English-language food recall announcements between 2012–2022. Each record is labelled with both a **HAZARD** and **PRODUCT**, which are further grouped into **HAZARD-CATEGORY** (10 classes) and **PRODUCT-CATEGORY** (22 classes). The label distributions are heavily imbalanced—some hazard types and product categories are rare. We split the data into 5,082 training examples, 565 validation, and 997 test examples. The dataset also includes auxiliary meta-features such as YEAR, MONTH, DAY, and COUNTRY.

Figure 4: Class and Feature Distribution of the SemEval Data

Because key information may reside either in the TITLE, the TEXT, or both, participants could select which fields (or combinations) to use. The challenge thus tests robustness under variable signal presence and noise. A core methodological aspect of the challenge involved managing severe class imbalance due to the long-tail distribution of hazard and product categories shown in Figure 4.

5.2.3. Methods

The Food Hazard Detection Challenge was held as a part of SemEval 2025 (Task 9) and organized around two subtasks: **Subtask 1 (ST1)**, a coarse-grained classification of *hazard category* and *product category*, and **Subtask 2 (ST2)**, a fine-grained “vector” classification that required predicting the specific *hazard* and *product*. Both subtasks were formulated as supervised multi-class text classification problems, with macro-F1 (weighted toward hazard accuracy) as the main evaluation metric.

Figure 5: Timeline of SemEval Challenge

As shown in **Figure 5**, the competition proceeded through three structured phases on [Codalab](#):

1. **Trial Phase**, during which participants received labelled training data (5,082 instances) and unlabelled validation data (565 instances).
2. **Conception Phase**, in which participants could submit up to 100 trial runs per subtask, using previously unpublished validation data for preliminary leaderboard feedback.
3. **Evaluation Phase**, where a hidden test set (997 examples) was released, and each team could make a single official submission on previously unpublished test data which served as the basis for the final ranking.

Participants were required to submit both a **system description** (detailing preprocessing, model design, and data augmentation) and a **code repository** (e.g., GitHub). This structure ensured reproducibility and methodological transparency.

We released **three baseline systems** to provide starting points:

- A **TF-IDF + logistic regression** baseline for lexical benchmarking.
- A **BERT fine-tuning** baseline representing modern encoder-only transformers.
- A **prompting-based conformal prediction** baseline inspired by our previous CICLE framework (see Section 4.2), illustrating LLM-assisted classification and uncertainty calibration.

Each model could take as input different feature combinations: *TITLE*, *TEXT*, or both, along with optional metadata such as *COUNTRY*, *YEAR*, *MONTH*, and *DAY*. This flexibility allowed participants to test feature relevance and robustness across noisy and incomplete input signals.

5.2.4. Results

We received around 260 participant registrations, and 99 valid test submissions; 27 of these submitted full system descriptions.

Leaderboard Performance: For ST1, scores ranged from ~ 0.1426 to 0.8223 (macro-averaged F1 over composite labels). Top-performing systems used rich feature sets (TITLE + TEXT + meta) and generally outperformed simpler baselines (e.g. BERT alone ~ 0.667). For ST2, the task proved substantially harder: the top score was ~ 0.5473 , much lower than the leading ST1 score, and performance fell steeply after the top few teams.

Effective Strategies: Utilizing both TITLE and TEXT generally improved performance relative to using only one. Surprisingly, in many systems, TITLE-only models outperformed TEXT-only ones, likely due to titles being more concentrated signals. Across top systems, several strategies emerged as consistently beneficial (see **Figure 6**):

- **Task decomposition vs joint modelling:** Treating ST1 and ST2 separately generally performed better than trying a joint model. Some participants experimented with multi-task or multi-turn prompting, but these did not universally outperform simpler decoupled architectures.
- **Ensembles:** Weighted ensembling of multiple models boosted robustness. Some systems optimized ensemble weights via grid search.
- **Synthetic data augmentation:** Many systems used LLMs to generate extra samples to mitigate class imbalance, via paraphrasing, summarization + concatenation, or merging instance information.
- **Architectural equivalence:** No one transformer paradigm (encoder-only, encoder-decoder, decoder-only) overwhelmingly dominated—top systems across different architectures achieved comparable performance.
- **Class-weighting and resampling:** Applying focal loss, oversampling rare classes, or SMOTE was common to counter the skewed label distribution.

Figure 6: Comparison of Approaches Submitted to SemEval Challenge

5.2.5. Conclusions

In summary, the challenge shows that synthetic data from LLMs is a powerful tool to mitigate long-tail imbalance present in real world data like food incident reports. Ensemble learning and class balancing are effective levers to increase robustness. While no single transformer architecture dominates, models that combine richer features, reasonable data augmentation, and ensemble fusion tend to reach the top. The vector-level classification remains a clear frontier for future work, due to its significantly lower scores and higher confusion rates. For EFRA this challenge also provided us with competitive approaches to solving food incident classification. The best of these approaches also has been included on the EFRA Powerhouse infrastructure.

5.3. Food Recall Classification – EFRA Conceptual Model Annotator

5.3.1. Summary

In this section we present an **LLM-based AI model** capable of analysing *Food Safety Incident Reports* and transforming unstructured text into structured “knowledge nuggets” aligned with the **EFRA conceptual model**. The objective of the model is to analyse incidents reports to identify key information (such as hazards and affected products) and classify them within a **hierarchical multi-label classification (HMC)** system encompassing thousands of concepts derived from the public ontologies that form the EFRA conceptual model.

In recent years, **instruction-tuned Large Language Models (LLMs)** have emerged as powerful tools for text analysis. These models can perform annotation and classification tasks based on natural language instructions—known as *prompts*—thus reducing the need for extensive manually labelled training data. Their

versatility makes them valuable for a wide range of applications, from general-purpose tasks such as sentiment analysis and topic modelling to more specialized annotation challenges. Unlike earlier approaches that relied mainly on syntactic or keyword-based patterns, LLMs leverage contextual understanding and inference, enabling them to achieve high performance across languages and, in some cases, to approach human-level annotation quality. However, **hierarchical text classification**, where documents must be assigned to multiple categories within a structured taxonomy, presents challenges for LLMs. Large and complex label spaces can make direct prompting ineffective, leading to information loss, higher computational costs, and difficulties in distinguishing fine-grained categories. Traditional methods typically rely on fully supervised or semi-supervised learning approaches, which depend on large volumes of human-labelled data—often costly, time-consuming, and difficult to scale.

The EFRA Conceptual Model Annotator is implemented as an AI agent that extends the capabilities of traditional Large Language Models by integrating external tools, structured knowledge bases, and APIs. This allows the model to reason over complex inputs, retrieve relevant information, and iteratively refine its outputs. The result is a **JSON-LD representation** of each input document, semantically annotated according to the EFRA conceptual model.

This modular architecture allows different LLMs or processing components to be integrated depending on task requirements or available computational resources. Overall, the main contribution is a **hybrid agent framework** that operationalizes LLMs for *structured knowledge extraction and semantic mapping* in the food safety domain—bridging unstructured reports with interoperable, machine-readable knowledge representations aligned with the EFRA conceptual model.

5.3.2. Data

We evaluate our annotator model on a subset of 50 records extracted from the **Food Safety Incidents** dataset from Agroknow; the records have been manually annotated with respect to the **EFRA conceptual model** and used to evaluate a set of different LLMs (gpt-4o-mini, gemma, mistral7).

The EFRA conceptual model integrates several public ontologies to ensure interoperability and semantic consistency across food safety data sources:

- **EFRA Food Safety Hazard** - developed in the first year of the project and formalized using a SKOS model, provides a formal categorization of hazards.
- **AGROVOC** – A multilingual thesaurus developed by the FAO, covering food, agriculture, fisheries, forestry, and related domains. It contains over 32,000 OWL-based concepts available in up to 29 languages and supports data annotation, retrieval, and integration through standard semantic web formats (RDF, XML, JSON).
- **FoodOn** – An open-source ontology describing food sources, ingredients, processing, packaging, and product classification, enabling structured representation of food items and production processes.
- **ChEBI (Chemical Entities of Biological Interest)** – An ontology for representing molecular entities, particularly small chemical compounds relevant to biological and biochemical contexts.
- **GS1 GPC (Global Product Classification)** – A standardized global product taxonomy used for trade and product identification, organized in a four-level hierarchy (Segment, Family, Class, Brick) with optional attributes for finer classification.

These ontologies constitute the knowledge base used by the LLM agent for mapping the extracted information to known concepts. The manually annotated gold standard and the dump of the KB are publicly available as a dataset on Zenodo.

5.3.3. Methods

We implemented a Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG)-like entity linking pipeline to map free-text mentions in Food Safety Incident Reports to concepts in the EFRA conceptual model. The core idea is to combine an indexed Knowledge Base (KB) containing EFRA entities with a hybrid search layer that returns a small, relevant candidate set for the LLM to reason over. By constraining the label space presented to the LLM, this approach improves scalability and accuracy while keeping entity selection grounded in structured knowledge.

All entries drawn from the EFRA conceptual model and its constituent public ontologies were ingested into a KB and indexed for retrieval. During indexing we enriched records with:

- canonical labels and aliases,
- textual definitions and notes,
- ontology provenance and identifiers,
- precomputed embeddings for semantic search.

These enriched records enable both lexical and semantic matching and provide provenance information for downstream explainability.

Candidate generation uses a hybrid retrieval mechanism combining:

1. **Tensor-based (vector) search** - semantic similarity via dense embeddings to capture paraphrases and contextual matches.
2. **Keyword / lexical search** - exact matches and high-precision string matches (useful for product codes, acronyms, and highly specific labels).

The results of both searches are merged and de-duplicated; candidates are ranked using a lightweight re-ranking heuristic that considers retrieval scores, string similarity, and provenance signals. This produces a curated top-K candidate list for each mention.

The retrieval functions were integrated as callable tools within an LLM-based agent. The agent framework treats the LLM as one component in a structured workflow that can:

- call external tools (the search functions),
- store and retrieve intermediate results (memory),
- and iterate over partial outputs to refine decisions.

Figure 7: Logical Architecture of the EFRA Conceptual Model Annotator

The agent executes a stepwise plan for each report document:

- **Summarization** - normalize and condense the source text to reduce variability and focus downstream processing on salient content.
- **Entity identification** - extract mentions of hazards, products and other relevant entities using an extraction model or LLM prompt designed for high recall.
- **Candidate retrieval** - for each extracted mention, invoke the hybrid search API to obtain a ranked set of candidate entities/concepts from EFRA knowledge base.
- **Candidate selection** - the LLM receives the mention, normalized context, and the top-K candidates; it produces the final mapping(s) together with a concise rationale and a normalized confidence score.

Each step stores its outputs in an append-only memory store, so subsequent steps can access provenance, earlier rationales, and scores to support traceability and post-hoc review.

A defining characteristic of the proposed design is that different LLMs or extraction components can be swapped in depending on accuracy, latency, or cost requirements. The separation between retrieval and reasoning enables targeted improvements (e.g., better embeddings, refined alias tables) without retraining the entire pipeline. The scheme also facilitates possible evolutions of the system with a human-in-the-loop review: mappings below a configurable confidence threshold are routed to reviewers (and reviewer corrections can be logged as labelled data for iterative improvement).

5.3.4. Results

In our evaluation, we tested and compared **three LLMs** (differentiated by licensing, hardware requirements, and resource demands) on the task of hazard / product annotation (versus the *Incidents Annotator Gold Standard*).

- **GPT-4o mini (OpenAI)**: A smaller, faster, and more cost-efficient variant of OpenAI's GPT-4o model, optimized for reasoning, text generation, and multimodal understanding. It balances strong performance with lightweight resource usage.
Model size: ~8 billion parameters (estimated; OpenAI has not disclosed the exact size).
 Official link: <https://platform.openai.com/docs/models/gpt-4o-mini>
- **Mistral 7B (Mistral AI)**: An open-weight large language model trained by Mistral AI, focusing on high efficiency and quality for a 7 billion-parameter model. It's widely used for research and deployment in local or open-source contexts.
Model size: 7 billion parameters.
 Official link: <https://mistral.ai/news/announcing-mistral-7b/>
- **Gemma 3 4B (Google DeepMind)**: Part of Google DeepMind's Gemma family of open models, built for transparency, safety, and efficiency. The "4B" variant is tuned for reasoning and instruction following while remaining lightweight.
Model size: 4 billion parameters.
 Official link: <https://deepmind.google/technologies/gemma/>

We applied each of the three models to annotate hazards and products in the incidents' dataset, then compared their outputs against the gold standard (i.e. the *Incidents Annotator Gold Standard* in the dataset). The table below reports the precision, recall, and match counts of the EFRA Conceptual Model Annotator when used with each LLM. We compare a commercial model (GPT-4o mini), an open-source 7B model (Mistral 7B), and a lighter open model (Gemma 4B) to understand trade-offs in performance, resource usage, and licensing.

Our evaluation reveals that:

- **GPT-4o mini** demonstrates a clear advantage in both hazard and product annotation tasks.

- The performance gap is particularly significant in **product detection**, where the model's precision and recall are 0.46. This task involves distinguishing among approximately 5,000 distinct product classes, posing a substantial challenge.
- In contrast, **hazard annotation** is more constrained, focusing on around 150 possible classes.
- **Mistral 7B** follows closely behind GPT-4o mini in both tasks, with a precision and recall of 0.68 in hazard annotation and 0.38 in product detection.
- **Gemma 4B** lags further, with precision and recall values of 0.57 for hazard annotation and 0.35 for product detection.

Table 5: Evaluation Results of the EFRA Conceptual Model Annotator

Model / Metric	Precision	Matches
Hazard		
GPT-4o-MINI	0.80	40
MISTRAL 7B	0.68	34
GEMMA-3 4B	0.58	28
Product		
GPT-4o-MINI	0.46	23
MISTRAL 7B	0.38	19
GEMM-3 4B	0.35	17

5.3.5. Conclusions

These findings underscore the challenges associated with large-scale product classification and highlight the varying complexities inherent in different annotation tasks.

6. Conclusions

This deliverable has presented the outcomes of the experimental work conducted in the EFRA project. It consolidates the methodologies, tools, and empirical results obtained through a series of targeted experiments designed to evaluate the performance, efficiency, and applicability of advanced analytical models deployed within the EFRA platform.

The work addressed three main thematic areas:

- **Models required by EFRA pilots** - focusing on predictive analytics for food safety forecasting and risk assessment. The experiments demonstrated the effectiveness of multi-factor modelling approaches that integrate heterogeneous data sources (e.g. historical incidents, laboratory tests, and environmental indicators) to achieve substantial improvements in prediction accuracy and reliability.
- **Models supporting the greener efficiency of the EFRA platform** – where the emphasis was on enhancing computational sustainability. Innovative methods, including hybrid LLM architectures (e.g., CICLE), early-exit neural network strategies, efficient retrieval algorithms, and model compression techniques (e.g., APB), successfully reduced energy consumption and computational cost while maintaining state-of-the-art performance.
- **Other models for the EFRA platform** - focusing on explainability, interoperability, and semantic enrichment. These include the development of self-counterfactual explanations for text classification with LLMs, large-scale benchmarking through shared tasks on food recall detection, and the EFRA Conceptual Model Annotator for transforming unstructured incident reports into semantically structured knowledge.

The collective results of these experiments demonstrate that EFRA’s methodological framework effectively balances accuracy, interpretability, and sustainability. By combining machine learning, natural language processing, and semantic technologies, EFRA establishes a validated, scalable foundation for next-generation food risk analytics.

In conclusion, the deliverable confirms that the EFRA platform’s analytical components are technically sound, scientifically validated, and ready for integration and deployment. The outcomes directly support the project’s overarching objectives of building an efficient, explainable, and environmentally sustainable ecosystem for proactive food risk prediction and management.